

Responsible AI, SDGs, and AI Governance in Africa

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Abstract: More than ever before, AI is now an area of national strategic importance. This has become quite evident with the proliferation of national AI strategies since the first was launched in Canada in 2017. There is now an ever-growing body of national AI strategies especially in countries situated in the Global South. AI is seen as a key driver of economic development and the strategies describe how countries plan to exploit AI technologies to achieve national development goals. However, AI technologies also generate problematic and unintended consequences, and the national strategies often describe governance mechanisms for mitigating such issues. As the national development goals of many countries also align with the UN SDGs, this paper explores the relationship between responsible governance of AI, the attainment of the UN SDGs and the implications for African countries. The paper shows that there is a clear link between the development of AI and the attainment of the SDGs. Also, based on an analysis of two AI policy tracking repositories - the OECD AI Policy Observatory and Oxford AI Readiness Index – this paper shows how African countries have lagged behind countries in the Global South in terms of the development of governance structures for AI. This has far-reaching implications for the attainment of the SDGs and the paper provides recommendations in this area.

Keywords: AI, Responsible AI, SDGs, Ethics, AI governance, Africa.

1. Introduction

The current AI governance landscape is growing led by stakeholders from developed countries in North America, Europe and Asia (Jobin et al., 2019; Schiff et al., 2020). Available governance models therefore highlight AI designs, development and deployment with these contexts as well as peculiar societal interests, hopes, concerns, fears and values from these societies. However, there is a very limited and convincing narrative on AI from an African perspective despite the fact that Africa is at the cusp of digitalisation which in many ways will be informed by the application of AI. This is especially disappointing when we look at the discourse of how AI can play an important role in meeting some of the UN's SDGs (sustainable development goals). In particular, there is a vast array of AI narratives on how AI can be central to meeting health challenges, agriculture and education to mention a few of some of the difficult areas that Africa grapples with as far as sustainable development is concerned.

We, therefore, argue that without consideration of a responsible AI African narrative that considers aspects central to achieving SDGs in as far as overcoming some of Africa's challenges, it will be near impossible to overcome them. By responsible AI, we mean AI systems that are developed “along fundamental human principles and values, to ensure

human flourishing and well-being in a sustainable world” (Dignum, 2019). In particular, we argue for a narrative that addresses specific common themes that are evident in the current global discourse on AI and which evidently play a central role in shaping AI. These, it can be argued, will also be an important aspect in successfully applying AI-infused digitalisation. These common themes include ethics, policies, regulations and laws around having a responsible AI.

The aforementioned common goals are of particular importance because the use and application of AI bring about social and ethical concerns when not addressed properly. For instance, there are ethical concerns around privacy, autonomy, anonymity, dependency among others which can only be addressed within strong and stringent regulatory policies and laws that are not adequately addressed in the limited narrative on African AI that exists. For example, when we look at areas such as health, agriculture, education, the narrative is always a positive one on AI, which granted, is very good. However, there is very little of the ethical concerns related to these areas. Without addressing such concerns, meeting the UN’s SDGs will be near impossible for the simple reason that if there are no culturally sensitive narratives coming from Africa, there is a risk of Africa falling behind in terms of understanding its own ethical issues around AI and subsequently finding solutions to mitigate them.

2. Issues to be Addressed

The paper addresses how responsible AI governance in Africa can enable the achievement of SDGs. This will be done by exploring issues around the ethics of AI, governance arrangements of AI in Africa and providing recommendations as a way of addressing AI governance issues.

3. Objectives

The objectives of this paper are as follows:

1. To make a case for the development of AI governance structures in Africa that can assist in the achievement of the SDGs
2. To explain possible implications of the lack of governance structures of AI in Africa
3. To provide recommendations for the development of sustainable and responsible AI in Africa

4. What is AI?

AI means different things to different people in different contexts. It is a concept that describes a complex array of cutting-edge technologies that are given different meanings in literature and practice. AI is a concept that should be understood and applied in nuanced ways. It should not be taken as an inflexible concept. Saying that, Kaplan and Haenlein (2019) defined AI as the ability of a technological system to correctly interpret external data, to learn from such data, and to use those learnings to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation. It describes systems that can perform functions that are traditionally attributed to human beings only. These systems can be classified according to capabilities and functions. According to Kaplan and Haenlein, (2019) they can be classified as: artificial narrow intelligence (ANI) or weak AI – systems that can perform specific tasks and unable to autonomously solve problems in other areas; artificial general intelligence (AGI) which describes systems that are able to “reason, plan, and solve problems autonomously for tasks they were never even designed for” and finally artificial super intelligence (ASI) – systems that are conscious or self-aware and that are able to solve problems in other areas instantaneously. It is important to note that what is currently available globally including in Africa can be described as ANI. AGI and ASI remain

scientific possibilities. In Africa, ANI systems are being designed, developed and deployed in a number of areas including; healthcare, agriculture, public service delivery, finTech, banking, telecommunications, transportation, education and politics.

5. Methodology

To get an understanding of the Global AI Policy landscape, two AI policy tracking repositories were analysed for this paper. These are the OECD AI Policy Observatory which provides information on over 6000 AI Policy initiatives from 60 countries, territories and the EU (OECD.AI, 2021), and the 2020 AI Readiness Index developed by Oxford Insights and the International Research Development Centre (IDRC) which provides some indication of how governments have positioned themselves to take advantage of AI transformations (Oxford Insights, 2021). The Oxford Insight repository also contains a special category, the Responsible AI Sub Index which is a tool dedicated to measuring how responsibly governments make use of AI. These databases were considered because they are currently some of the most comprehensive and widely used AI policy tracking repositories. Also considered was the outcome of the study by the European Parliamentary Research Services (EPRS) Panel for the Future of Science and Technology STOA (European Parliament Directorate-General for Parliamentary Research Services, 2020). This document was consulted because it devotes a considerable section to national and international Strategies on AI and is considered an authority on AI issues in some quarters.

6. The Case for Responsible AI Governance

A case is made for the development of governance structures of AI in Africa. We do this by first exploring the link between AI and SDGs. This is followed by a description of the AI policy landscape and an analysis of the possible implications of a lack of AI governance in Africa. We then discuss the role of responsible AI in attaining SDGs in Africa. Lastly, we provide recommendations for AI governance arrangements.

6.1 AI and SDGs

There is enough demonstrable evidence that suggests that AI can play a significant role in accelerating development in many domain areas in both the Global North and the Global South. For the Global North, in particular, this is seen in a number of policies on AI as captured in the methodology section that discuss the benefits of AI for society but also around academic discourse and research on not only the potentials and capabilities of AI on the one hand but also on the challenges that AI presents (Aicardi et al 2021). Further, the application of AI in industry (King et al, 2019), education (Luckin et al, 2016) and healthcare (Bartoletti, 2019) illustrate its importance in current times and for the future. AI's importance in meeting sustainable development agenda's is equally articulated by the United Nations (UN). For instance, since 2017 to date, the UN has held several Summits on the importance of AI for sustainable development under the title 'AI for Good', therefore indicating that AI can play a pertinent role in meeting its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). There is an increasing number of use cases for AI that can enable the achievement of the SDGs. Using the numerous capabilities of AI, there are continual efforts to accelerate the attainment of SDGs globally, with a lot of emphasis being directed to the Global South, specifically to the African continent (Trotter, 2021; Uthmann, 2021). Several examples have been available in literature which show the relation between AI and how the technology could be used to accelerate the attainment of SDGs. For example, Jean et al (2016) and Sachs (2015), point to the potentials of AI in satellite mapping and data analysis of poverty which is a direct reference to SDG1 on No Poverty. In reference to SDG 2 on Zero Hunger, Agbozo (2018) and Vinuesa et al (2019) touch on the predictive analysis that AI allows in Agriculture which can result in increased productivity when automated drones

and satellites are used. In as far as SDG 3 on good health and well-being is concerned, scholars like Boman & Kruse (2017); Panda & Bhatia (2018); Wahl, Cossy-Gantner, Germann, & Schwalbe (2018) discuss the benefits of AI on this SDG. They posit that the use of AI in healthcare will be in the forefront of diagnostics and scientific breakthroughs. In any development to be achieved, innovation and the infrastructure to allow for such innovation (SDG9) is important. It is precisely for this reason that Sachs (2015) and Wakimoto (2018) reveal that AI and its related technologies of IoT sensors and 4D printing are reshaping industries and therefore offering innovative possibilities for development. Further examples of where AI may be applicable for Africa's sustainable development is in SDG16 which is concerned with peace, justice and strong institutions. In support of this, Scholars like Vinuesa et al. (2019) as well as Hudson (2019) and Krawczyk & Targowski (2019) are of the opinion that AI can play a role in reducing discrimination and corruption while also being innovatively applicable in e-government to order to offer more personalized and responsive intelligent services. They also add that AI has the potential to have an impact on global cyber threats.

These examples suggest that AI has the ability to improve the lives of people and bring societal benefits in many different ways and areas. Stahl (2021) alludes to the fact that AI can allow for human flourishing through its ability to offer deeper insights into different phenomena that humans cannot do on their own including predictive analysis, diagnostics, the offer of smart and intelligence services among others. Although the seventeen SDGs are universal and important, some are more pertinent to the Global South due to the social and economic position it finds itself in. For instance, the 2020 Africa SDG Index for Africa reveals that the main challenges are around good health and wellbeing which is associated with SDG3; infrastructure which is associated with SDG 9 and peace and justice associated with SDG 16. That stated, the index further reveals that despite the stated challenging SDGs, Africa is faring slightly better in SDG 13 (climate action) and SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production)' (p.6) (The Sustainable Development Goals Center for Africa and Sustainable Development Solutions Network, 2020).

As health and well-being is one of the greatest challenges and because it can impact many aspects of people's lives if not tackled well, the rest of this section will pay close attention to the SDG 3 challenge and what applying responsible AI might mean particularly in relation to AI structural policy and governance for the Global South. Owoyemi et al (2020) point to the more meaningful application of AI in healthcare in more developed countries than in Africa for instance and fear that if this continues, Africa may not reap the rewards that come with AI which includes a projected saving of \$150 billion by 2026 in healthcare costs when AI is applied.

An indication of the opportunities for AI in Africa can be seen in the various applications of this technology in various domains. For example, Akpanudo (2022) identifies several areas where AI has been deployed for healthcare delivery in Africa. It includes – the use of Fuzzy expert systems in South Africa to capture expert knowledge and historic data that integrates climatic biophysical parameters with epidemiological data to identify risk potential of a cholera outbreak; An AI based app called 'Ubenwa' that was developed in Nigeria and enables the diagnosis of asphyxia in infants through automated analysis of a baby's cry and can help to prevent infant mortality; the use of AI for diabetic retinopathy diagnosis in Zambia; and the use of AI to identify fake drugs in Nigeria or use of AI to predict health care longevity in public service in South Africa. Another area where AI is being used gainfully in Africa is in the Agriculture sector. In Cameroun, an AI start-up called AgriXTech has developed an AI based application that helps farmers tackle the problem of crop pest and plant diseases through early detection and identification of suitable treatment. A similarly project in Kenya referred to as the Third Eye project uses AI in combination with historical data in drones fitted with infrared cameras for agricultural

surveys to diagnose diseases, identify pests, and to determine nutrient deficiencies.

While all of these indicate opportunities for development of AI initiatives in Africa Owoyemi et al (2020) argue that it pales in comparison to the application of AI in the Global North due to a number of concerns. The issues include but are not limited to the quality of data and its availability, the lack of robust legal and policy regulatory frameworks, AI costs and a lack of adequate and necessary infrastructure. To harness the full benefits of artificial intelligence in Africa, more must be done by governments in Africa to address these issues by enabling a supportive environment for research and development in this field, as well as to financially incentivise and support such initiatives.

A reliance on AI applications that are not developed by the Global South and for the Global South, may see countries from there, particularly those in Africa being left behind or playing catch-up. For example, most if not all the top AI companies dealing in healthcare sectors such as healthcare are from the Global North, with some taking their services to Africa. These include companies like Caption Health whose technology has been used in Kenyan schools since 2016 to help with rheumatic heart disease symptoms, and Atomwise, a San Francisco AI outfit that has used its AI technology to help with the development treatment for the Ebola virus (The Medical Futurist, 2020).

Also, reliance on outside developers, who are generally from the Global North may also mean that African countries do not have a say in how the data collected is managed and even if it did, due to a lack of AI policy and governance structures, it becomes difficult to play on a level playing field with those with technical know-how and capability to develop AI. This means the AI gap is further widened rather than reduced, therefore making for increased inequalities and an unequal playing field in the application of responsible AI in healthcare. As such, although there can be pockets of AI initiatives that can be pointed to in Africa which for all intents and purposes are a good development and a step in the right direction, the fact that such initiatives are mostly being developed and owned by countries from the Global North means that SDGs like reduced inequalities will prove challenging in being met in areas such as AI innovation in healthcare when it comes to the Global South.

However, if well thought out and with robust AI policy structures in place, the Global South, in particular Africa, can benefit from AI application. Specifically, this can be in reducing the healthcare personnel gap of which gap leads to long waiting periods for those in need of healthcare. The use of AI in this regard means that patients can be attended to sooner than later as is often the case and that the diagnosis and detection of ailments can be done more quickly and efficiently. As a result, the upshot of this would be improved service delivery and improved access to healthcare.

6.2 The AI Policy landscape

The above discussion has provided some indication of how AI can enable the attainment of the SDGs especially SDG3 which focuses on good health and well-being, as well as some of the issues that African countries must overcome to achieve this. One issue that has been pointed out and that will be further explored in this section relates to the lack of policy and governance structures and how this can exacerbate already existing societal inequalities and an unequal playing field in the application of responsible AI. A similar point has already been made in relation to regional inequalities in the UK (Oxford Insights, 2020) where it has been stressed that the UK has some of the worst regional inequalities in the developed world and that a change of strategy is required to ensure that the benefit of AI is equally distributed in across regions of the UK. Similar situations in other parts of the world have enabled a gradual shifting of the discourse on AI ethics/responsible AI into the political realm and many governments have begun to create national strategies that can enable responsible use of AI.

What has become apparent is that the most active countries in the AI policy and governance landscape are situated in the Global North and particularly come from places like the United States of America (USA), Europe and Asia. However, there is very limited participation from countries in the global south, especially from Africa which is at the cusp of digitalisation and the application of AI. This is especially disappointing considering that the discourse of how AI can play an important role in meeting some of the UN's SDGs. In particular, there is a vast array of narratives on how AI can be central to meeting health challenges, Agriculture and education to mention but a few of the difficult areas that Africa grapples with as far as sustainable development is concerned.

The first country to develop a national AI strategy is Canada. In 2017 the Canadian Government invested \$125 million for the creation of a Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy (Canadian Institute for Advanced Research - CIFAR, 2021). Although the strategy has as its central focus the advancement of national AI initiatives, it also seeks a better understanding of the societal implications of AI and the development of thought leadership on the ethical and legal implications of the advancement of AI. It must not be forgotten, however, that this strategy is Pan-Canadian in every sense of the word and as such, Canadian interests at its core. Despite being the first country to propose a national AI strategy, Canada has been ranked at the 11th position in the Responsible AI Sub Index.

Nevertheless, the USA is at the top of the AI readiness index. One of the important reasons for this relates to the leading role that the country plays in the investment and development of AI technologies. It is interesting to note that the government of the country has backed the AI development effort by an Executive order on "Maintaining American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence" which was issued in 2019. Among other things, the Order aims to ensure continued American leadership in AI to maintain the economic and national security of the United States and to shape the global evolution of AI in a manner that is consistent with American values, policies and priorities. While the Order recognises the need to foster public trust and confidence in AI through the protection of civil liberties and privacy, its emphasis on American values cannot be lost. In line with this, the American "National Artificial Intelligence Research and Development Strategic Plan" (Select Committee on Artificial Intelligence, 2019) which was first published in 2016 (Networking and Information Technology Research and Development Subcommittee, 2016) was updated inter alia to reflect the emphasis on American Values in addressing the ethical, legal, and societal implications of AI.

In Europe, there is recognition that sustainable economic growth and societal well-being increasingly relies on the value created by data and AI systems. There is also a recognition that to enable this, Europe must combine its industrial and technological strength with a regulatory framework that is based on its fundamental values (Roy, 2020). It is no wonder then, that the European Commission has actively promoted the development of national AI Strategies by member states and has led by example in developing a European Strategy. This can be seen in two Communications of the Commission released in 2018 titled 'Artificial Intelligence for Europe (European Commission, 2018a) and 'Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence' (European Commission, 2018b). Within a year of this call, 16 of the 28 countries in the Union had completed the process of developing national AI strategies, while 5 others already had a draft and 6 others had started taking concrete steps in this direction (Roy, 2020). The development of these strategies along with AI Initiatives and strong investments in the AI sector has resulted in many European countries ranking among the highest in the AI readiness index (Oxford Insights, 2021). For example, the UK was ranked 2nd globally, followed by Finland, Germany, and then Sweden in the government AI readiness Index.

Not surprisingly, African countries are ranked among the lowest in the AI readiness index. According to Oxford Insights (2021), this should come as no surprise as African

countries have historically lagged behind the rest of the world in technological developments. Of the 54 countries in Africa, barely 5 countries have an AI readiness index that is above the world average. Even then, these countries, led by Mauritius, and then followed by Egypt, South Africa, Seychelles, and Tunisia are only very slightly above the world average. One reason why Mauritius leads other African countries in the ranking is that in 2019, it was the first country in Africa to publish a fully developed AI strategy. The government has also established national AI bodies including an AI Council to support the government's drive in developing an AI ecosystem. Similarly, one of the main reasons Egypt follows Mauritius in the ranking is because it was quick to develop a national strategy which was published in 2019. It has also set up a national AI council to supervise the implementation of the national AI Strategy and followed this up with the passing of a data privacy law in 2020. The rest of the African countries (including all the countries from the west and central Africa) score extremely low in the world of AI readiness rankings and Oxford Insights (2021) pegs this mainly to the dearth of relevant governance structures such as appropriate regulatory and ethical frameworks for AI in these countries. Other reasons include low investment in the AI sector and infrastructure limitations including lack of data repositories.

7. Lack of AI Governance in Africa: Possible Implications

AI is a value-laden technology and globally, AI governance has become a critical tool to ensure that AI applications are designed with values that align with the common good. As pointed out in the section on AI Policy landscape, these governance mechanisms that set the agenda for AI ecosystems (technical, legal, ethical, organisational and socio-cultural) to thrive are lacking in Africa. Although huge investments by multinational companies such as Google, IBM Research, Microsoft, Facebook, Twitter and Amazon together with initiatives by African AI experts trained in the global North (such as Deep Learning Indaba, Zindi and Data Science Africa) are creating an emerging AI ecosystem in Africa, Africa's biggest companies are not zealously championing the cause of AI design and implementation. The growth of AI in Africa is being championed by foreign multinational companies and small and innovative Technology start-ups. But as AI continues to gain traction, the paucity of AI governance becomes more glaring considering the fact that African values, interests, expectations and fears may be ignored in the design and deployment of the systems. This section provides insights on the implications of the continued absence of Africa in the global AI policy landscape; including the exacerbation of the global power imbalance, culturally insensitive design of AI applications as well as the emerging concerns related to bias and unfair discrimination.

7.1 Exacerbation of Global Power Imbalance

Defined as the “asymmetrical relations of power among persons, institutions or states” (Girvan, 2007), power imbalances characterise the historical inequalities or divide between the global north and the global south generated by sequential industrial revolutions (Monge-Naranjo and Ueda, 2019). From interpersonal, local, national, regional to global relations, AI (which is driving the Fourth Industrial Revolution) is set to redraw the map of the global balance of power. Thus, most developed countries in the North are engaged in the metaphoric ‘AI race’ which has now incorporated the question of who sets the global guidelines for AI. Engaged in these efforts include governments from the North, multinationals, international organisations and think tanks. Given the availability of established data infrastructure, computational power and government interest and investments in technology, AI systems that profoundly affect economic development, social justice and human rights as well as guidelines that shape them are being developed in the north.

However, many have noted that AI discourses are amplifying voices in the north alone although the technology has increasingly become pervasive in the south which touches on the global power relations in which AI systems are built. Africa is missing in the global discussions on AI governance which implies that the current AI governance landscape lacks ‘global’ perspectives. That Africa is missing in the global landscape of AI governance means African interests, values and principles are not taken into consideration which raises concerns about exacerbating the already existing power imbalance between the north and the south. If the power to design and govern AI continues to accumulate in the hands of a few, the risks of misuse could be greater in the global south with far-reaching implications for development and democracy. It is not sustainable to have the north build the technology and develop the guidelines for global design and implementation because global power imbalances will be deepened. The consequential impact AI has in societies across the world provides an argument to push for the inclusion of all relevant voices around the world in the articulation of the ways in which AI systems will be governed. We suggest that this starts as a bottom-up initiative where societies reflect on their contextual values, principles and expectations of what AI systems should align with.

7.2 Possibility of Culturally Insensitive AI Design and Deployment in Africa

The literature on AI and value alignment is now well established (van de Poel, 2020; Gabriel, 2020). AI is designed to align with “instructions, intentions, revealed preferences, ideal preferences, interests and values” (Gabriel, 2020). As moral and ethical values and principles are increasingly formulated for AI to adhere to by groups such as IEEE and the EU High-level Expert Group on AI, there remains a critical question of ‘whose values and interests’ should be embedded into the design and deployment of AI? This is particularly important because some of the suggested values such as fairness, respect for autonomy, trust and transparency mean different things in different cultural contexts. The order and priority of values in the global north are not always similar to those in the global South. This means that AI systems are currently designed to promote the value systems of the global north and this may be problematic for countries in the global south. Most notably these values are being pushed through AI governance mechanisms. Therefore, without such a governance framework in Africa, the interests and values of Africans will likely not be factored in. The risk is that a culturally insensitive AI design and deployment will definitely have negative impacts on society. The possibility of such negative impacts underlines epistemic approaches such as ‘value sensitive design’ and ‘human-centred design’ in AI.

7.3 Risks of Unfair Discrimination and Bias

Despite the huge benefits AI promises, many AI applications have problems of unfair discrimination and bias due to a lack of diversity of data or the algorithms behind them. AI-based biased and discriminatory decisions have very far-reaching and unintended effects on people. Such decisions and effects have been documented in healthcare (Ledford, 2019), judicial systems (Miron et al., 2021), education (Baker and Hawn, 2021), surveillance (Raji et al., 2020) and financial activities (Hassani, 2021). The growing body of literature on AI ethics is very clear that black people, women and disadvantaged parts of societies are disproportionately affected by AI bias and discrimination. This highlights the importance of principles and values to ensure that AI does not exacerbate existing biases or even introduce new ones that can harm Africans. The UNESCO draft recommendation on the ethics of AI is unequivocal in declaring that “We need international and national policies and regulatory frameworks to ensure that these emerging technologies benefit humanity as a whole” (Ad Hoc Expert Group AHEG, 2020). Given that Africa still lacks the robust data infrastructure and the large amount AI skillsets that can provide sufficient diversity for AI design and

deployment, governance mechanisms to ensure that risks of unfair discrimination and bias are mitigated should be prioritised.

7.4 Possible Effects on the Achievement of SDGs

In their study on the role of AI in the achievement of SDGs, Vinuesa et al., (2020) found that while AI can enable the attainment of 134 targets across all the SDGs, it can also inhibit 59 targets. Similarly, Gupta et al., (2021) in reporting the conclusion of an expert panel discussion on AI and sustainability stated that 79% of the 17 SDGs can be positively affected by AI, while 35% may be negative. These conclusions corroborate other reports that indicate that AI can have both positive (Jean et al., 2016; Tomašev et al., 2020) and negative impacts on SDGs (Courtland, 2018; Sætra, 2021). These negative impacts are informed by well documented AI issues such as unfair biases and discriminatory nature of some AI systems, its very high energy requirements, and possible influences on human autonomy (Vinuesa et al., 2020). To make AI a sustainable enabler to development, therefore, there is a need to harness the positive impacts while mitigating the negative impacts which is the role of responsible AI. As a continent aiming to attain the UN SDG targets, there is sufficient evidence to suggest that Africa needs to harness the benefits of AI through robust and empirically sound governance structures grounded in clear epistemological understandings.

8. The Role of Responsible AI in SDGs in Africa

As noted in previous sections, AI is expected to play an important role in achieving the UNs SDGs. The Technology Facilitation Mechanism (TFM) set out in Paragraph 70 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development for example recognises the important role that technology innovation can play in achieving the SDGs. However, in doing so, it becomes imperative to also recognise and therefore anticipate unintended consequences of technologies such as AI. One way of doing this is by ensuring that there is responsibility in the use, adoption and application of AI particularly in as far as AI policy is concerned. Without robust AI governance structures, for instance, it becomes a challenge to 'build the resilience of the poor and those in vulnerable situations and reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate-related extreme events and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters' as tabulated by SDG1 indicator 1.5. Although we note that AI can play a role in agricultural productivity and therefore contribute to SDG2 of achieving zero hunger, without adequate AI governance structures to guard against other environmental pressures that can result, achieving this SDG can be a challenge.

The introduction of innovative technologies in healthcare has its concerns especially when it comes to the use and adoption of AI where there are no relatable AI policy structures in place. For instance, the use of mobile phones and related apps raise serious concerns around the privacy and security of patient data that are not currently addressed in law. In particular, it may not be the case that data access is only via doctors and patients but that data can be accessed and is managed by non-healthcare professionals who may have the technical know-how but not the adequate training in patient confidentiality as do health care professionals. If such data were to land in the wrong hands, it can have negative social implications.

The COVID pandemic has also revealed that there can be social barriers to achieving SDG3 for good health and well being when there is no equitable access to quality technology between those who can afford and those who cannot afford innovative technologies in healthcare, and in particular in the fight against the covid pandemic. Daramola et al (2021) argue for the use of AI in the fight against COVID-19 in Africa's healthcare systems. He posits AI can be used to enhance the safety of health carers. Additionally, Wakunuma et al (2020) note the use of robots in the fight against covid and in

keeping health carers safe in Rwanda. However, more of these initiatives are needed in Africa. This can only be done with adequate AI governance structures in place that can tackle the ethical concerns that may arise as AI is applied.

9. Recommendations

This paper explored the relationship between responsible AI, governance and SDGs and the implications for Africa. Although AI presents a vast opportunity to substantially contribute to the attainment of the SDGs, including reduction of hunger and poverty, affordable energy, clean water and sanitation and quality education to mention a few (Vinuesa et al, 2020), for Africa to fully tap into the benefits of AI, a number of structural reforms need to be made that takes into recognition the socio-cultural peculiarities of the continent.

First of all, it has been noted that Africa faces key challenges, including limited governance structures. It is important to establish AI governance structures that will facilitate the effective development and implementation of AI. According to the Web Foundation (2017), the lack of policy regulation remains a concern for African stakeholders. Improved regulation and governance structure will therefore help to build trust and encourage early adoption of AI in Africa. The existence of a governance structure for AI would help African governments to address the technological, political, social, legal and ethical questions raised by AI innovation and develop a framework for the adoption of AI policies and initiatives that enhance not only the legal and regulatory framework but also the business environment that supports technological innovation whilst also protecting citizens. A critical step towards this is the establishment of innovation-friendly data governance structures to manage the availability, integrity, quality, usability and security of African data sets for optimal maximisation. It is important that frameworks and policies are in place to ensure responsible processing of data at each stage of the data life cycle from collection to deletion. Whereas Africa can learn from international best practices of data governance for AI, it is imperative that Africa develops country-specific national strategies that create an environment for AI to thrive. In order to achieve this, effective regulation should be designed to address issues such as privacy and data protection, intellectual property and industry-specific regulations (for example, fin-tech, agriculture and health sector) that can help to address challenges and harness the potential benefits of AI in Africa. Furthermore, national and regional AI Councils need to be established to oversee the orchestration and implementation of AI strategies as well as open data initiatives that will foster transparency and accountability of AI development. This also includes the creation of 'AI Labs' at both national and regional levels to facilitate research and development that would impact on policy and governance of AI.

Secondly, there is the need to promote African ethical principles and cultural backgrounds that can shape the design and implementation of AI in Africa. One way to achieve this is by emphasizing the role of individuals and the community in AI ethics. It is important to identify core African values and principles that can be embedded into AI design and implementation. African cultural contexts are characterised by communitarian principles of interconnectedness, solidarity and sharing. Some of the ethical frameworks that can be highlighted here include *ubuntu* which focuses on the common good, tolerance, mutual respect and value for human life (Langat et al, 2020). This notion of collectiveness should be extended to the ethics of AI technologies and automated systems. As noted by Hoesle (1992), the use of technological innovation systems requires users to think and act in predefined western ways that already marginalizes developing jurisdictions such as Africa due to the origin of computerised systems in these western cultures. It is therefore important that African values and cultures should be incorporated into technological models for Africa that transcends beyond national, regional and continental boundaries.

Thirdly, it has also been noted that Africa faces the challenge of limited stakeholder consultation which exacerbates the ability to fully realise AI potentials (Access Partnership, 2018). Therefore, creating and strengthening a framework for coordination among stakeholders including aligning policies and regulations will help to create an enabling environment for AI to thrive. There is a need for improved collaboration between industry, policymakers, researchers and social scientists. One way to achieve this is through funding directed towards energised and productive AI infrastructure. Furthermore, due to the fact that AI in Africa is still at a rudimentary stage compared to the rest of the world, the continent can benefit from a diversified funding ecosystem that includes government, international partners and African Philanthropists to encourage AI research and innovation (AI4D Report, 2021). Funding will also help to address issues around discrimination and bias datasets. Whilst Algorithmically-driven innovations can encode discrimination and bias that can further exacerbate already existing societal inequities. It is therefore important that African stakeholders work together to ensure the development of an inclusive, equitable and sustainable AI data ecosystem for Africa that recognises diverse socio-cultural interests and values of the continent.

Finally, for Africa to fully harness the potential of AI to achieve SDG targets, it is very important that AI is embedded into schools' curricula. Education is always a key driver for AI and for Africa, the impact of early education in AI development cannot be over-emphasized. In view of this, African governments should develop future educational structures that incorporate AI core competencies into educational systems from primary through to tertiary levels that provide an understanding of AI processes and possible abuse in order to raise a generation that develops skills to safely utilise AI including the protection of personal data.

10. Conclusions and Summary

This paper has explored the relationship between AI governance and SDGs in Africa. We have so far established that Africa lacks a robust AI governance ecosystem that can ensure that full AI capacities are harnessed to enable the achievement of the SDG targets. Of particular importance is SDG3 on health and well-being. Whilst this can positively impact on the Global South, analysis of the AI policy landscape reveals the lack of an enabling environment for AI to successfully thrive in Africa. These include the lack of regulatory and ethical frameworks and also inadequate technologies that make it increasingly difficult to orchestrate and deploy AI solutions in Africa. This lack of AI governance structures has clear implications that include possible exacerbation of global power imbalance, the possibility of developing culturally insensitive AI systems, exacerbating the risks of unfair discrimination and finally the possibility of negative effects on achieving the SDG targets in Africa. Whereas AI governance will not provide solutions to all possible AI challenges in Africa, it is a good foundation that can drive responsible AI design and implementation. Therefore, we recommend that stakeholders from industry, policy, academia and civil society groups should collaborate more to promote AI research on African datasets and algorithms that can enable the consideration of African contextual concerns, interests and values. Other recommendations include the promotion of African ethical principles, the establishment of AI governance structures and reasoned integration of AI into educational programs in Africa.

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